

Psithurism

Dedication: To the Motherland

Englebert B. Mangaldan, PhD

*Director, Indigenous People Education Research Center
Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College*

Nature speaks, nature whispers
Everywhere and every time
Mother Nature communes
To all beings, seen and unseen
To all men, young and old
In the rustling of the leaves
As blown by the winds
Mother Nature is talking
Heed, ponder, feel
I am near, am here, said She.

She makes known her presence
Not in the conscience of men
Not in the pages of every paper
Nor in the hands of time
Not even in the busy noise
Of streets and vehicles
Of man-made sounds
And intercourse of men
Not with the thunder
Nor pouring of the rain.

When Mother Nature,
Whose love is pure
When good tidings
To men She brings
Message of peace
Of hope and love
Of comfort and joy
She wants to share
With the rustling of leaves
She summons the winds.

The rustling of the leaves
Behold the winds
As she flaps her wings
Listen to silent whisper
Carried by the breeze
Feel the caress
And magical embrace
Music to the ears
Is the rustling of the leaves.

When trees do sway
In elegance and dance
See their mystic grace
Their canopy like waves
Listen to the winds
Savour the scent
Of this heaven's sent
Then you shall know
Someone is watching you.

Mother Nature
Who loves us sure
Wants us to rest
Our weary soul
She lulls us to slumber
Rock in a cradle
Sound of wind
And rustling of leaves
She carries away
Our fears and dismay.

If we only know
How to listen with our hearts
And not with the ears
If we could see
What the eyes can't see
There is music
In the whistling of the winds
Soothing is the rustling of leaves
It calms the mind
Relieves the limbs.

If there is more lovely
Like flowers in the meadow
Majestic than sunrise
With the morning dew
Hypnotic than the moon
On cloudless night
Nothing but the angelic
Rustling of the leaves
As the wind kiss her cheeks
Oh, gentle is the wind.

When body weary
Laden with anxiety
I come before thee
As a child would be
The breeze you bring me
Is a sweet melody
Brings relief
Mine spirit and body
Thy wind, thy breeze
Heavenly the rustling of the leaves.

The courtship of birds
On every tree tops
And the cheering of cicadas
All juxtaposed
In unified accord.
But the coming of the wind
A relief, revitalizing indeed
With the rustling of leaves
Would complete
The joy we seek.

I shall not want
To wander far beyond
Journey into solitude
A desire deny me not
Immerse with Mother Nature
Find solace in her womb
When the wind blows
leaves in rhythm rustle
Someone is talking
She is whispering.

Nature is me and so with you
Nature we see, everywhere is she
The echoes of the thunder
the hush of waterfall yonder
The flight of the birds
the chirping of cicadas
The bridge of rainbow
the roaring of the rapids
One with nature and nature are we.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18886555

*Copyright & Published in the Philippines ©2026
by Pinagpala Publishing Services*